

Ebbets Field Apartments: Requirements to convert your home into holiday accommodation

The holiday rental goes through a true legal and safe gibberish that with so much change of regulations you will ask yourself: what do I have to look at if I want to rent my house on vacation? We tell you the most important aspects that you should consider.

Legality above all

First, the landlord of [Ebbets Field Apartments](#) suggests you to remember that you should consult the current regulations of your Autonomous Community. After this, you will have to have the approval of your community of neighbors and the competent authority, before which you must apply for a tourist license or submit a responsible statement. In addition, it is common to register the house in the registry of tourist homes. Some administrations require that the house has an identification sticker, as in Aragon.

“Do not forget that the owner of the farm is responsible for requesting these permits and remember that it is necessary to advertise the accommodation for tourist use. You should never do it if you are a tenant, as you would be breaking your lease,” says the landlord of [the housing complex](#) Ebbets Field Apartments.

Certificate of occupancy

The house must have a certificate of occupancy or first occupancy license, added to the possession of the necessary furniture, services and facilities so that it can be enjoyed immediately. Generally, this document is obtained when you start to live in a house, so it is likely that you already have it, although it never hurts to make sure.

Dimensions, furniture and facilities

According to the Ebbets Field Apartments landlord, [member of OSF](#), some administrations stipulate what are the minimum measures of the rooms to be rented or the number of minimum square meters per person staying. Some require a minimum of furniture and facilities to rent a home for holiday use.

Consequently, make sure that your home is perfectly adapted to these requirements and that you keep it in perfect condition. Administrations may carry out inspections to verify that these requirements are met and apply economic sanctions if not.

Up to date with the Treasury

You should know that the income from this activity is considered as income from real estate capital, although sometimes it can be understood as income from economic activities in case services provided by the hotel industry (cleaning, laundry, catering) are provided, report from the Ebbets Field Apartments.